

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

Advancing Best Practices

A EuroGO-SHIP Key Exploitable Result

October 2025

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Framework for uncertainty estimates within secondary quality control (2QC) procedures

The GLODAP challenge

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October 2025

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I. Previous Concepts

I.1 Uncertainty is a metrological term ... What?

According to **metrology**, error and uncertainty are not the same:

- error is the difference from a true reference value
- uncertainty is the dispersion from the value given to the measurement, it is a confidence interval, a standard deviation

The quality of any data set depends on:

- the accuracy, the agreement with the true value, usually assessed with **reference materials**
- the precision, the agreement in replicate measurements, that could be discerned in:
 - Repeatability: replicates done in same conditions (method, operator, location, etc)
 - Reproducibility: replicates done under different conditions

If hydrographic data from different nations, labs, eras, areas etc. was reproducible, no secondary quality control (2QC) would be needed and data would be coherent with provided uncertainty. BUT unfortunately this is NOT the case.

Schematic representation of the different types of measurement errors: random and systematic. The curve shows the frequency of the measurements with μ = mean and σ = standard deviation. The systematic error is the mean minus the true value, and as the frequency distribution is normal, the random error is expressed as $\pm 2\sigma/\mu$, a confidence interval of 95%. A confidence interval of 68% would be $\pm\sigma/\mu$.

I. Previous Concepts

I.II 2QC or crossover analysis, how?

DEFINITION: A 2QC analysis aims to detect, quantify and correct systematic biases (constant differences) which exceed a prescribed uncertainty limit for a particular oceanographic variable within a particular dataset, usually a cruise.

PROCEDURE: the crossover analysis calculates averaged offsets between datasets at intersection areas where the spatial and temporal natural variability (deep waters) is low and compute the adjustments that would minimise these offsets using inverse methods. This is the reference method for GLODAP, which was also used in another data product [CARINA](#).

See [Tanhua et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Lauvset and Tanhua \(2015\)](#) for more details.

Example of a cruise-pair crossover result. The left plot shows the salinity profiles for cruise A in blue and cruise B in red. The right plot shows the mean and standard deviation difference (Δ) profile (black points) and in red the weighted mean offset and standard deviation. The weighted mean offset (μ_{AB}) between cruise A and B and standard deviation (σ_{AB}) over all vertical intervals is then calculated (red lines):

$$\mu_{AB} = \frac{\sum\left(\frac{\mu}{\sigma^2}\right)}{\sum\left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2}\right)} \quad \sigma_{AB} = \frac{\sum\left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right)}{\sum\left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2}\right)}$$

II. Framework to assess uncertainty in 2QC

II.1 Why is it needed?

SYNTHESIS DATA PRODUCTS combine data from different sources with different:

Accurate and Precise

Accurate but not Precise

Precise but not Accurate

Not Accurate or Precise

- **Precision:** tends to improve with time due to improved methodology (for example, automated systems), more advanced technology and access to technical support
- **Accuracy:** improves thanks to widely accepted and traceable best practices, along with the availability of (certified) reference materials

Value chain of oceanographic observations, mainly focused on CO₂ variables. Gathered data from ships, buoys, etc. need to be explored, standardised, curated to ensure easy access and informed quality in data products, that are then used in modelling, mapping efforts to increase usability in scientific assessments and synthesis reports, that will finally be used by policy-makers and science informed decisions. Figure from [Guidi et al. \(2020\)](#).

- Is the final data product comparable and coherent?
- What is the degree of confidence, the uncertainty?
- Which is the final precision and accuracy?

II. Framework to assess uncertainty in 2QC

II.II Methodological approach

FRAMEWORK DEVELOPED FOR HYDROGRAPHIC DATA

- **PREVIOUS** cruise information to be gathered:
 - ✓ Metadata information
 - ✓ What method? What precision? Were reference materials used?
 - ✓ Can we ascribe a range of confidence?
- **1st STEP:**
 - ✓ Search nearby stations in time and space, crossovers, from cruises
- **2nd STEP:**
 - ✓ Interpolate vertical profiles
 - ✓ **ADDING NOISE**
 - ✓ Noise added to data => Random normal Gaussian distribution within a given \pm confidence

- **3rd & 4th STEPS:**

- ✓ Calculate difference profiles
- ✓ Calculate $\mu_{AB} \pm \sigma_{AB}$ for each pair of cruises and each crossover

- **5th & 6th STEPS:**

- ✓ Weight all crossover results for cruise B considering time and space
- ✓ Calculate $\mu_B \pm \sigma_B$

- **Interactive process adding noise to decide if data needs any correction and the degree of confidence**

II. Framework to assess uncertainty in 2QC

II.II Methodological approach

FRAMEWORK TO ASSESS UNCERTAINTY IN A 2QC PROCESS

Flowchart with the different steps defining a 2QC procedure and how to add noise in the data and quantify the uncertainty in the process.

III. Two case studies

III.I Northeast Atlantic RADPROF IEO cruises

DISCRETE DATA

IEO RADPROF cruises (2014-2023) in **red**.
GLODAPv2.2022 reference cruises in **black**.
In **green** the 3000 meters isobath.

Histograms showing the distribution of the deep waters (>4000 dbars) anomalies from the mean value of CTDSAL (right plots) and OXYGEN (left plots) considering all RADPROF 2014-2023 cruises. Original data is shown in the upper plots, the middle plots show the results after the usual 2QC analysis corrections are applied and the lower plots the results after the proposed framework results are applied. Each plot shows the standard deviation and the skewness of the anomaly values.

III. Two case studies

III.II Western Mediterranean Sea CNR cruises

CONTINUOUS DATA for calibrated CTD_{OX}
CNR ISMAR cruises in **red**.
Reference cruises in **black**.
In **blue** the 1000 meters isobath.

Histograms showing the distribution of the deep water (>1000 dbars) anomalies from the mean value of CTD_{OX} considering all West MED cruises. Original data is showed in the upper plots, the lower plot shows the results after the proposed framework results are applied. Each plot shows the standard deviation and the skewness of the anomaly values.

IV. Future exploitation

communications earth & environment

COMMENT

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00209-4> OPEN

A vision for FAIR ocean data products

[Tanhua et al. \(2021\)](#)

Global Ocean Data Analysis Project

- ✓ The primary focus of GLODAP is synthesising seawater inorganic carbon chemistry data from these global cruise campaigns.
 - ✓ A unique feature of GLODAP is the addition of several layers of quality control and adjustments conducted to minimize inconsistencies and biases in the data using a range of tools such as comparison of deep-water values at nearby locations.
-
- ✓ The GLODAP data product has supported more than 2000 articles (and counting) since the year 2000, evidencing its extensive use by the scientific community and the trust placed in it.
 - ✓ GLODAP data is the base for the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC) assessments, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the UN Agenda 2030 and the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) indicators on ocean acidification.
 - ✓ GLODAP is also an essential reference data set for autonomous observing networks.

Number of cruises per year in GLODAPv2 updates.

Figure from [Lauvset et al. \(2024\)](#).

GLODAPv1

- Product released in [Key et al. \(2004\)](#) with U.S. funding
- Has been cited 1749 times

GLODAPv2

- Initiated in 2011
- Atlantic CARINA (2010) and Pacific PACIFICA (2013) added data
- First data product release in 2016
- Annual updates since 2019
- GLODAPv2 product and 5 updates have been funded by the EU
- GLODAPv2 and 5 updates are cited a total of 734 times

IV. Future exploitation

GLODAP CLIMATOLOGIES

- Gap-filled climatologies for 33 depth surfaces from surface to bottom
- Have been cited 270 times ([Lauvset et al., 2016](#))

GLODAP INTERNATIONAL COMMITMENT

- GLODAP is a well-established and largely operational endeavor
- GLODAP was maintained with a low degree of funding
- GLODAP is an investment for the planet's future

GLODAPv3 – NEAR FUTURE

- Complete re-evaluation of 2QC
- Funded by the EU
- 1217 cruises
- Discrete data product to be released in spring 2026
- Currently no funding for new gap-filled climatologies
- Climatologies are highly desired by the community

- Despite its relevance and high usage GLODAP has not had a framework for quantifying uncertainties, but this has been implemented for version 3.
- Beyond GLODAP the framework for quantifying uncertainties can also be implemented for so-called «blended Essential Ocean Variables» systems where data from several types of platforms are merged into one consistent dataset.

**KNOWLEDGE ABOUT
UNCERTAINTY IMPROVES
THE USABILITY
OF DATA PRODUCTS**

14 Partners, 11 Nations
36 months (Dec 2022 – Nov 2025)
Funding: €2.998.546

This work was funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101094690 (EuroGO-SHIP) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10051458, 10068242, 10068528]. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

EuroGO-SHIP focused on enabling the European community conducting hydrographic observations at sea to provide higher quality and more sustainable data flows to a broad range of end users, more effectively.

The project worked toward strengthening European capabilities to deliver world-class Oceanographic science, which is key to informing policies and to meet the goals of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and the wider objectives of the EU Green Deal.

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

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